

Description scientifique du projet

- **Titre du projet :** High-fidelity physics-based earthquake simulations : seismic vulnerability assessment of the Cadarache nuclear site.
- **Responsable scientifique :**¹ (nom, prénom) : GATTI Filippo (Maître de Conférence) - filippo.gatti@centralesupelec.fr
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- **Laboratoire :** Lab. Mécanique des Sols, Structures et Matériaux (LMSSMat) UMR CNRS 8579 CentraleSupélec - Université Paris Saclay
- **Nombre d'heures scalaires (mono-processeur) demandées :**

Partition CPU Jean Zay (HPE CSL) :

3.000.000 heures scalaires

1 Note

The motivation behind the following project is the positive response (below) received for the last year call *Grands Challenges sur Jean Zay*. We repropose the same main ideas of the mentioned call, although we readdressed the main target to the investigation of the seismic response of the Cadarache nuclear facility.

1. Le responsable se charge du suivi du projet et fournit un bilan en fin d'année.

Paris, le 24 mai 2019

Objet : candidature « *Grand Challenges* » sur la machine Jean Zay.

Cher Monsieur Lopez-Caballero,

Nous vous remercions pour l'envoi de votre proposition de grand dé sur la machine Jean Zay. Après l'avoir étudiée attentivement en concertation avec le Président du Comité Thématique dont dépend la discipline de votre projet, nous sommes au regret de vous informer que nous ne pouvons le retenir essentiellement par manque de ressources sur la machine dans un contexte prévisible de très forte concurrence.

Cependant, conscients que votre projet est pleinement adapté à l'utilisation du calculateur Jean Zay et d'un intérêt scienti que majeur, il mériterait d'être retenu lors de notre prochain appel régulier DARI A7 auquel nous vous encourageons donc désormais à postuler.

En vous remerciant pour votre implication dans la recherche scienti que.

Très cordialement,

Denis Girou
Directeur de l'IDRIS

Philippe Lavocat
PDG de GENCI

2 Context, challenges and general objectives

Episteme is a philosophical term derived from the Ancient Greek word *ἐπιστήμη*, which can refer to *knowledge*, *science* or *understanding* and which comes from the verb *ἐπίστασθαι*, meaning *to know*, *to understand*, or *to be acquainted with*. In this sense, earthquakes are one of the most complex natural phenomena for scientists to understand and predict. This high uncertainty, coupled with their disaster potential, increases the overall associated seismic risk. The latter can be assessed by either following a deterministic approach (i.e. by directly modelling the physics behind the ground shaking phenomenon) or by either considering a fully probabilistic approach (basing on the statistics drawn from previous strong ground motion observations). However, in areas of moderate seismicity, such as metropolitan France, a general lack of direct observations limits the extensive application of non-linear data regression, due to scarcity of available recording databases. This drawback clashes with the demand of updated seismic safety margins for critical structures and infrastructures (nuclear power plants and dams especially). Given the fact that the majority of them has been constructed a few decades ago, French authorities face the urgency of a general reassessment of the seismic safety margins foreseen at the design stage, exploiting the gathered knowledge in seismology, earthquake engineering, the new geophysical and geological data, as well as the new technological tools available. Nuclear facilities, dams and other important infrastructures must undergo extensive *stress testing*, to assess and update their status and functionality, in case an unexpected (at the design stage) earthquake occurs. This commitment fosters the definition of site-specific studies (the Cadarache nuclear site for instance) which can now be virtually tested via high-fidelity *digital twins*.

For a long time, geophysicists and seismologists have exploited rather *simplified* and *generic* seismological models, based on closed form solutions of the viscoelastic wave propagation problem, in simplified geological media (e.g. considering the Earth's crust as sub-horizontally layered visco-elastic half-space). Many crucial issues have been neglected, due to the intrinsic complexity of the analytical models and the general lack of data to quantify them :

- the heterogeneities in the Earth's crust (at regional and site scale)
- the non-linearity of shallow soil deposits
- the surface topography
- solid-fluid interaction (coastlines, bathymetry etc)

Although the mentioned numerical models were capable of reproducing reasonably well the P, S or Rayleigh waves arrival times and the main reflections within the Earth's crust, they were generally limited to the very low-frequency part of the radiated spectrum (0-1 Hz). On the other hand, the seismic design of critical structures (such as nuclear power plants) requires reliable input motion in a broader frequency band, ranging within 0 and 30 Hz : reactor and turbine buildings are very stiff and rigid structures, with non-negligible resonance modes at frequencies higher than 10 Hz. Moreover, a broad-band input motion is required whenever the nuclear facility equipment (piping system for instance) is taken into consideration.

This incompatibility trenched seismologists and structural engineers apart for a long time : the transient dynamics of aboveground structures (eventually with soil-structure interaction at the site scale) has been traditionally studied separately, by employing selected spectrum-compatible recordings as input motion.

In recent years, the ever increasing availability of computer power and related numerical methods paved the way to deterministic exploration of the scenarios space, compatibly with the degree of knowledge of focal issues, such as :

1. the 3-D geological structure of the Earth's crust
2. the geomechanical properties of soil deposits and deep bedrock
3. the surface morphology (topography, bathymetry, coastlines)
4. the characteristics of the active faults (tectonic context, slip patches, focal mechanisms)

This *physics-based* numerical approach thrives nowadays : many historical strong ground motions have been successfully reproduced by HPC-based numerical codes, providing subtle insights on the anatomy of the earthquakes [5, 10, 14, 18, 19, 22, 24, 31, 33]. An impressive result was obtained by a Chinese research group, who run a non-linear earthquake simulation over a continental 320 km by 312 km by 40 km region, up to 18 Hz [26]. The use of octrees has made possible a high degree of scalability in mesh generation using up to 220.000 cores [12]. Moreover, high-fidelity modeling widened the research horizons concerning the study of complex features such as the attenuation and coherency of coda wave in the seismic signals [2], the directivity and the incoherence of the wave motion near-source [32], the non-linear site effects [27] among others.

So far, very rare are the examples of complete fault-to-structure interaction studies, with strong Soil-Structure Interaction coupling (see for instance [16, 29, 42]). The most reliable and efficient method was proposed by Bielak et al. [8], called the Domain Reduction Method. It consists into a two-step analysis, declined as follows : (i) regional scale wave-propagation in simplified geological medium (typically the deep visco-elastic stratified Earth's crust), not including the non-linear site-effects ; (ii) a second run of the analysis on a smaller domain (eventually adding the structure) delimited by an artificial boundary at which equivalent inertial forces and free-field velocities, obtained in the precedent step, are applied. Quinay et al. [17] applied this method to study the structural response of the Kashiwazaki-Kariwa Nuclear Power Plant (KKNPP) in a fault-to-structure framework, up to 1 Hz.

Albeit the outstanding results obtained by HPC physics based modeling, due to its ontological determinism and to

the large computational costs at stake, the methodology is still hardly adaptable to tackle large parameter sweeps, provided with the high level of uncertainty related to geology, source and site, convolved with the numerical dispersion. Moreover, uncertainty propagates through the model, which must be quantified when performing seismic risk assessment of critical structures by exploiting synthetic time-histories.

In this project, we aim at constructing an earthquake scenario space for the Cadarache nuclear site (France) at the occurrence of extreme ground shaking events. This represents one of the major goals of the PIA² project SINAPS@³, benefited from French state funding managed by the National Research Agency under program RNSR Future Investments bearing reference No. ANR-11-RSNR-0022-04⁴. For this purpose, a strict collaboration with Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives (CEA) and Institut des Sciences de la Terre (IsTerre) is established, in the framework of the SINAPS@ ANR project. The paradigm we pursue seeks the progressive integration of high-fidelity numerical simulations and recorded data, towards robust hybrid earthquake prediction. Figure 1a shows this paradigm schematically. We intend to tackle this challenge by employing an efficient HPC multi-tool platform developed jointly by MSSMat UMR CNRS 8579 Laboratory (CentraleSupélec), CEA and Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris (see Figure 1b), capable of simulating broad-band non-linear seismic wave propagation in highly heterogeneous media, from the fault to the aboveground structures (i.e. at a regional scale).

Figure 1: (a) Scheme of the modelling paradigm adopted ; (b) modular representation of the numerical platform developed by CentraleSupélec, CEA and IPGP

The computational platform has proven itself capable of efficiently handling complex surface topography, coastlines and bathymetry, 3-D geological configurations and large fault discontinuities [Gatti et al'2019, 28, 32, 35, 36]. For instance, we studied the seismic response of the KKNPP, during the $M_W 6.6$ 2007 Niigata-Chuetsu-Oki earthquake (NCOEQ), central west-coast of Japan, reaching a maximum frequency $f_{max} = 7$ Hz, in a computational domain of $60 \text{ km} \times 60 \text{ km} \times 60 \text{ km}$, with a minimum grid size of $200 \text{ m} \times 200 \text{ m} \times 200 \text{ m}$, with minimal shear wave velocity of 700 m/s [35]. Similar earthquake scenarios are currently being run for the Argostoli site (a European test site, where a vast geophysical and tectonic survey are currently carried out), within the framework of the A0040410444 and ongoing A0060410444 call on OCCIGEN supercomputer. For the Argostoli test case, we managed to perform our largest physics-based high-fidelity numerical simulation of a main shock earthquake scenario ($1.3 \cdot 10^{10}$ degrees-of-freedom), reliable up to a maximum frequency of 10 Hz (see Figure 4), in the softest part of the domain (i.e. where shorter wave lengths must be correctly discretized). A paper has been recently submitted [Gatti et al'2019]. Table 1 give an insight on the main features of this last outstanding result. Moreover, the outcome of the simulation has been deeply analyzed by [40, 41].

N_E	N_D	$\mathcal{L}_x \cdot \mathcal{L}_y \cdot \mathcal{L}_z$ [km^3]	$\Delta_x^{min} \cdot \Delta_y^{min} \cdot \Delta_z^{min}$ [m^3]
$\approx 4.5 \cdot 10^6$	$\approx 9.8 - 13.5 \cdot 10^9$	$44 \times 44 \times 63$	$130 \times 130 \times 35$

Table 1: Mesh characteristics for the earthquake scenario of Kefalonia island [39] (model O5). N_E : number of hexaedrael elements (8-nodes) ; N_D : number of Degrees of Freedom ($10 \times 10 \times 10$ GLL $\times 3$ per element) ; $\mathcal{L}_x - \mathcal{L}_y - \mathcal{L}_z$ domain sizes ; $\Delta_x^{min} - \Delta_y^{min} - \Delta_z^{min}$ minimum element sizes.

2. Programme d'Investissements d'Avenir
3. <https://www.institut-seism.fr/en/projects/sinaps/>
4. <https://anr.fr/ProjetIA-11-RSNR-0022>

Figure 2: Results of the earthquake simulation run on OCCIGEN (allocation A0040410444). (a) Velocity contours along the fault plane and in the shallow crustal sediments at Argostoli site (Greece); (b) synthetic interferogram in the surroundings of Argostoli basin [Gatti'et'al'2019]

However, the dynamic structural response of a reactor building of a nuclear power plant covers a 0-30 Hz frequency range. Therefore, the synthetic incident wave-field generated in the surroundings of the structural components must be enriched at frequencies $f > 10$ Hz. Due to the poor quality of information on the geological features required to characterize the wave motion at $f > 10$ Hz, this high-frequency ground shaking is simulated via artificial neural networks (this machine learning techniques is called ANN2BB [38]) and added to the low-frequency ($f < 10$ Hz) part obtained via numerical simulation Figure 3 illustrates the two stages of the ANN2BB procedure : the neural network is first trained on records (REC), Figure 3a) and then applied to the low-frequency part of the ground motion ($T > T^*$, correspond to the accuracy limit of PBS, in terms of natural period) predicted by Physics-Based Simulations (PBS) to predict the short period chunk of the response spectrum S_a ($T < T^*$) and obtain Broad-Band (BB) synthetic ground motion.

Figure 3: Scheme of the hybrid earthquake modelling strategy, called ANN2BB : (a) training phase of the algorithm, performed on recorded database (REC); (b) prediction phase of the algorithm, performed on Physics Based Simulations (PBS) into Broad-Band (BB) synthetic records.

In this way, high-fidelity earthquake simulations can be exploited to construct a large brand-new site-specific broad-band (0-30 Hz) database, to be used as input motion for Finite Element models (FEM) of the reactor building and of its structural components. Figure 4a presents the strategy adopted to couple the outcome of SEM3D, after being enriched at high frequency via ANN2BB, as incident ground motion to feed the FEM structural model of Unit 7 reactor building, at KKNPP [37]. Figure 4b shows the good agreement obtained between synthetic prediction and recorded one. In this manner, we were able to predict the seismic response from the fault to the structure, by employing our high-performance and high-fidelity platform, including seismic wave generation at the fault discontinuity, its propagation through the Earth's crust, the Soil-Structure Interaction (SSI) and the structural dynamics.

Figure 4: (a) Scheme of the coupling strategy between Spectral Element Method (SEM) for regional propagation of the seismic wave motion and Finite Element Method for the structural components. Boundary Element Method (BEM) is employed to solve the SSI problem; (b) Pseudo-spectral acceleration response (predicted, red, and recorded, black) at the foundation of the Unit 7 reactor building at KKNPP.

3 Specific objectives and expected results

As mentioned, the target of this project is the Cadarache test site (see Figure 5a), located in the surroundings of the Moyenne Durance fault (FMD, see Figure 5b). This area presents a complex geological formation that includes several faults [13]. A very interesting insight on the seismic context⁵ in the region is presented in [23]. This study evaluates mainly a close active fault that was discovered as reactivated fault in the last years [20] (see Figure 5a). Furthermore, paleoseismic studies revealed that a M_W 6.5 occurred between 26000 and 9000 years ago [7]. Our main purpose is to provide an estimation of a plausible M_W 6.5 strong ground motion generated at ≈ 15 km away from the critical structures (the EOLE building in Figure 5b).

Figure 5: (a) DEM of the region of study; (b) Location of the point source and extended source in the region of Cadarache

Figure 5b shows an example of fault scenario considered in our analysis. The picture indicates the location of the sedimentary basin (grey) where the Cadarache facility is located. Details on the mean regional geological model, on the surface topography and on the fault geometry are provided by the CEA. An image of the preliminary numerical model is shown in Figure ??

The novelty of this project are two :

- fostering *hybrid* earthquake simulation, where high-fidelity earthquake simulations can be exploited to

5. https://www.irsn.fr/FR/connaissances/Installations_nucleaires/La_surete_Nucleaire/risque_sismique_installations_nucleaires/Pages/11-Sismotectonique_de_la_faille_de_la_Moyenne_Durance.aspx

Figure 6: 3-D Hexahedral mesh of the Cadarache region

construct brand-new site-specific databases of synthetic ground motions (thanks to ANN2BB meta-model, for instance) to be used to evaluate the seismic vulnerability of the nuclear facilities ;

- explore the scenario space with some *modal* numerical simulations, so as to produce further plausible realizations off-line with reduced computation time but keeping high accurate site-specific prediction.

Specifically, the idea we pursue is to run a set of *modal* scenarios in the frequency range 0-10 Hz, for different realizations of fault geometry, slip patch, focal mechanism (see for instance [34]). The simulated seismic response in the surroundings of the Cadarache site will be used afterwards, to assess its seismic vulnerability and to construct the *response surface* of the main structures. The use of machine learning techniques can improve the synthetic outcome and provide reliable, broad-band (0-30 Hz) strong ground motion realizations, over a large region. Moreover, for each fault scenario, we aim at compute site-specific Green's tensor functions $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}^{site}$ (third-order tensor), corresponding to a number of point sources deployed across the fault plane Σ . Those Green's functions are exploited to generate thousands of different strong ground motion scenarios, thanks to the so called Empirical Green's Function method (EGF [15]). With this approach, the site seismic response is reconstructed off-line as a convolution between the pre-computed Green's functions and several random realizations of slip distributions across the fault plane. The EGF method is based upon the representation relation proposed by Aki and Richards [3], which writes :

$$\underline{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{x}; t) = \int_{\Sigma} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}^{site}(\mathbf{x}, t; \underline{\xi}, \tau) * \underline{\mathbf{m}}(\underline{\xi}, \tau) ds(\underline{\xi}) \quad (1)$$

where $\underline{\mathbf{m}}(\underline{\xi}, \tau)$ represents the *seismic moment tensor* (i.e. the equivalent forces generated by a point-wise source, considered as a displacement discontinuity) and $*$ the time convolution operator. $\underline{\mathbf{m}}(\underline{\xi}, \tau)$ depends on the focal mechanism (the fault plane orientation) and on the time-varying slip patch across the fault plane. In the EGF method the integral in Equation 1 is approximated by the discrete sum over the number of point sources N_S employed :

$$\underline{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{x}; t) \approx \sum_{n=1}^{N_S} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}^{site}(\mathbf{x}, t; \underline{\xi}_n, \tau) * \underline{\mathbf{m}}(\underline{\xi}_n, \tau) \quad (2)$$

Given this brief explanation, we envisages to perform $N_S = 10$ point source simulations of ≈ 30 s, deployed across the fault plane, as shown in Figure 7a. Preliminary tests, performed on FUSION cluster (Mésocentre Moulon) showed that the composition of 10 moment tensors and Green's function (via Equation 2) provides very good approximation of the extended fault simulation (both in terms of time history and duration, as shown in Figure 7b, both in terms of spectra, as shown in Figure 7c).

Given the fault-site relative locations, as shown in Figure 7a, we would like to apply the EGF method to two scenarios : (1) mean rupture path directed along the largest fault direction, i.e. NE-SW ; (2) mean rupture path directed along the shortest fault direction, i.e. NW-SE. In this way, we will be able to characterize the Cadarache seismic response along *fault-parallel* and *fault-normal* directions.

The overall amount of estimated runs is 22 (2 fault scenarios, 1 extended fault simulation + 10 point-source simulations). The generated scenario will be exploited a training basis for ANN2BB and other generative machine learning algorithms we are currently developing, based on numerical simulations.

Figure 7: (a) Map of the Cadarache site, the FMD and 10 point sources to approximate the seismic response with EGF method ; (b) example of time-history obtained via EGF method for the Cadarache site ; (c) Fourier's spectra obtained via EGF for the Cadarache site

4 Codes, dependencies and performances

We have recently developed (jointly with CEA and Insitut de Physique du Globe de Paris) an efficient multi-tool computational tool, called SEM3D [25], capable of simulating broad-band non-linear seismic wave propagation in highly heterogeneous media, from the fault to the aboveground structures. The core of the platform is represented by a Spectral Element (SE) Method code, tailored to solve 3-D wave propagation in anisotropic, randomly heterogeneous and non-linear geo-materials. The experimental design (ED) foreseen for this project is constructed by SEM3D analyses. However, the platform is featured by a series of other computational tools that help in constructing large scale numerical scenario of an earthquake event, namely :

- HexMesh⁶ : a scalable octree-based mesh generation code ;
- randomField⁷ : a scalable random field generator over large computational domains, based on the spectral generation technique [4].

The parallel octree-based mesh generator is able to treat immersed geometries with high scalability in executions. It was tested up to 6561 processing cores. The mesh can be non-conforming, composed exclusively by hexahedral elements, or it can be made conforming using tetrahedral elements. Non-conforming meshes have hanging nodes, (i.e. nodes located inside edges or faces), which restricts its use to numerical methods that provide support for this type of nodal interpolation. In particular, efficient parallel implementation of the SEM requires the use of conformal hexahedra. Owing to the SEM spectral convergence, higher resolution is obtained by p -refinement (i.e. by increasing the polynomial order) rather than by increasing the number of linear elements (common practice in Finite Difference/Element schemes).

6. <https://github.com/jcamata/HexMesh.git>

7. <https://github.com/cottureau/randomField.git>

Figure 8: Weak scalability curves obtained for SEM3D, expressed as number of time rate of mesh elements processed varying the number of MPI process employed. In blue, the linear scalability curve represents the ideal *optimum* result (perfectly linear scalability). Green and red lines portray the *worst* and *average* performances instead.

The random field generator employs the sum of a series of N_ϕ cosines with random phases/amplitudes [6], sampled over fine regular grids [28]. The Fast Fourier Transform can be used to bring the complexity of this generation method to $\mathcal{O}(N_\phi \log N_\phi)$. The field is then re-interpolated over the not uniformly space-distributed SE grid (featured by 5 to 10 Gauss-Lobatto-Legendre points per dimension). When dealing with large domains, the scalability issue is solved by generating smaller independent realizations, supported on overlapping subdomains (in a distributed memory parallel scheme), and then recomposed together into the full domain.

Finally, the non-linear wave-propagation solver exploits the high resolution of the spectral element method with efficient explicit algorithm to integrate non-linear rheology representing the non-linear cyclic behaviour of soils. In the following, the peculiar features of the mentioned computational platform are described.

Non-linear wave propagation : SEM3D

SEM3D [25] is mainly conceived for applications in geophysics, with the aim of considering realistic 3-D complex geo-structures. It is written in Fortran 95, and uses MPI. The I/O is performed using parallel HDF5 libraries. The meshes are non-structured and composed of conformal hexahedra by employing METIS⁸ library. The discretization in space is based on spectral elements in space and an explicit scheme in time (both for elastic and non-linear case). The spectral element method is a variant of the finite element methods which uses high-order Lagrange polynomials on Gauss-Lobatto-Legendre (GLL) points. The corresponding quadrature ensures that the mass matrix is diagonal. Hence, inversion of the mass matrix at each time steps is not costly and very short time steps, imposed by the explicit scheme, are not an issue. The code was tested on several clusters, including Curie (by CEA) and the Mésocentre de CentraleSupélec and ENS Paris Saclay (SGI ICE X) and GENCI OCCIGEN (c20150447417, A0040410444, A0060410444). Moreover, it has been run on the 64-nodes Bi-Opteron cluster of Service de Calcul Parallèle de l’Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris (a model with 25 millions degrees of freedom, running over 128 cores). A previous version of the code (less efficient in terms of parallelism [30]) was tested on Jade, in a previous GENCI project (c2010046485). On these occasions, the weak scalability of the spectral element solver has been demonstrated. Finally, it should be noted that a code with similar features and structure (although developed by a completely different team) was ported on the largest clusters available (see for example [9], 15 years back). An example of weak scalability curve obtained for SEM3D is shown in Figure 8. SEM3D has been run over more than 4096 cores. Moreover, given the experience of recent allocations on OCCIGEN, a comparison between SEM3D performances obtained on FUSION (cluster of Mésocentre Moulon) and OCCIGEN was drawn, to check our estimations in terms of required CPU-hours. Ten simulations are hereafter compared : F1-F5, run on FUSION, O1-O5, run on OCCIGEN (see the specifics in Table 2). Figure 9 shows the performances obtained, compared to the original (CP) and corrected-blind (BP) prediction (made before allocation A4). First and foremost, we noticed a very good agreement between the corrected prediction CP and F1 and BP and F4, which justifies our prediction made on FUSION.

However, we needed some preliminary iterations (corresponding to simulations O1-O3) to replicate the same performances obtained on FUSION (in terms of CPU-time). Specifically, preliminary simulations O1-O3 (performed without the CINES support, before the mid-term allocation) showed a increased computation burden (expressed as t_{CPU}/t_{EQ}). For instance, O2 and F4 represents the same simulation, although we obtained a CPU-time per second real time simulation t_{CPU}/t_{EQ} [h/s] of 1.82×10^3 h/s for FUSION and 3.49×10^4 h/s for OCCIGEN respectively. Iterations O4-O5 were performed thanks to the CINES support : the same performances were obtained for FUSION

8. <http://glaros.dtc.umn.edu/gkhome/views/metis>

Figure 9: CPU-time per real earthquake simulation t_{CPU}/t_{EQK} , for different DOF numbers. BP and CP correspond to the blind and corrected-blind predictions respectively (see mid-term allocation).

	N_{EL}	N_{GLL}	N_{MPI}
F1	2×10^6	5	648
F2	-	7	648
F3	-	10	648
F4	18×10^6	5	648
F5	4.5×10^6	5	216
O1	-	5	4800
O2	-	5	648
O3	-	7	648
O4	-	5	4800
O5	4.5×10^6	5	4000
CP	2×10^6	5	216
BP	18×10^6	5	648

Table 2: Earthquake numerical model. N_E : number of hexahedral elements (8-nodes); N_{GLL} : number of GLL points per element); N_{MPI} : number of CPU cores.

and OCCIGEN on the same test case : $t_{CPU}/t_{EQK} = 1.772 \cdot 10^3$ h/s for OCCIGEN vs t_{CPU}/t_{EQK} [h/s] of $1.82 \cdot 10^3$ h/s for FUSION. This iteration validates SEM3D portability on OCCIGEN. In the following, we transitioned towards a higher number of DOFs by improving the numerical model of Argostoli (see the mesh characteristics in Table 1), previously run on FUSION (F5). On OCCIGEN, the same numerical model was considered (called O5), its accuracy being increased by p -refinement, i.e. by increasing two times the GLL points per edge (resulting in $10 \times 10 \times 10$ GLL points per element), for a total $\approx 13.48 \cdot 10^9$. We successfully simulated a 20 sec earthquake strong ground motion, consuming around 81100 CPU hours [Gatti et al 2019]. For O5-F5, we also included the new code feature represented by the extended fault seismic source. Expected performances were attained (quasi-linear scalability) and we successfully passed the limit of 10^{10} DOFs (never before achieved on FUSION), thanks to the possibility of running jobs over > 720 CPU - cores (current limitation for FUSION).

Finally, a heuristic rule of thumb was inferred from previous experience : optimal performances were observed when 10000 hexahedral elements, each featured by $N_{GLL} = 5 \times 5 \times 5$, are processed per node, considering a standard node memory of 2 Gb.

Octree-based Mesh Generation : HexMesh

Octrees are hierarchical data structures that allows the decomposition a three-dimensional space in regular cubes, called octants. The initial octant normally surrounds all the input domain and is divided in 8 equally spaced cubes - the child octants. Each of these children could be subdivided again, in a recursive process that is usually limited by some criteria (i.e. maximum number of subdivisions, minimum octant size). An octree can be implemented by a tree structure or by a linear octree, where only octants with no children are stored. In this last representation, as also known by linear octree, each leaf is stored as a unique integer - called locational code - which identifies its position and depth level in the tree. Among the benefits of linear octrees is the implicit representation of intermediary octants (non-leaves), making it memory efficient, and better performance on sequential access. Additionally, by not making use of memory pointers, parallel implementation of the linear octree has a lower overhead in interprocess communication (in comparison to other tree structures [11]). We have implemented a set of algorithms that address the special needs of parallel octree meshing. These algorithms are : (i) Octree initialization algorithm that guarantees that all processes have at least one piece of the linear octree. (ii) Refinement algorithm that decompose the octants according to some refinement criterion (i.e. maximum size or position relative to the geometry boundaries), and 2 :1 balancing algorithm that ensure that no neighbor octants differentiate in more than one level [11]. This last algorithm is important because a balanced octree results in more smooth transitions between elements, a feature that has a direct influence on the final mesh quality. It also guarantees that the resulting mesh will not have more than one hanging node for each edge or face, reducing the complexity of conforming mesh process. The resulting code has been written in plain C and makes use of MPI only. The code runs on any standard cluster. A previous version of the code (generating non-conformal hexahedra and conformal tetrahedra meshes) has been tested at Stampede Dell cluster (at TACC) and on a SGI ICE 8400 and on a Oracle cluster in Brazil. Table 3 presents a weak scalability test performed on the mesh of the Kefalonia region (Greece). The communication time (last column) attains a fairly constant percentage of the total time. The code has run over 6561 MPI cores.

Figure ?? show an example of a mesh generated by HexMesh.

Cores	Levels	Nodes	Elements	Time (s)	Comm(%)
81	7	85,602,744	83,102,679	12.061	21 %
243	8	769,790,232	747,937,476	32.994	20 %
729	9	6,926,153,724	6,731,438,013	105.188	25 %
6561	10	62,330,385,168	60,583,119,264	123.066	29 %

Table 3: Weak scaling of the mesh generation for the Kefalonia region in Greece. Cores : number of MPI cores; Levels : octree refinement level; Nodes : number of mesh nodes; Elements : number of mesh elements; Time : generation time; Comm : percentage of the total elapsed time for communication operation.

Random Field Generation : randomFields

The heterogeneous properties of the Earth’s crust are included in our modelling strategy for large scale earthquake scenarios. In this context, by *large* we refer to a domain size L much larger than both the correlation length ℓ_C (or some characteristic size of the fluctuation) and the discretization step h . It is therefore advantageous to represent those fluctuations a scalar random fields (for instance, representing the spatial distribution of the shear-modulus). Those large random fields can be effectively sampled over a coarse grid (with a step size relevant for the correlation length) and then interpolated onto the mesh of interest (provided by the GLL (Gauss-Lobatto-Legendre) grid used in SEM3D). If the discretization step is much larger than the correlation length, the sampling becomes simple and numerically inexpensive. Indeed, for the mesh considered, the random field is essentially a white noise with Gaussian first-order marginal density [21]. The first-order marginal density is modified locally by combining a direct and inverse Rosenblatt transforms [1]. randomField uses the spectral quadrature formula proposed by [6] to generate the random field, taking advantage of the Fast Fourier Transform algorithms (using the library FFTW⁹). The code is written in Fortan95 and exploits HDF5 data structures for I/O operations. To efficiently reduce the generation time for large L/ℓ_C values, randomField is implemented in a highly-scalable *localized* fashion, exploiting MPI. Independent realizations are generated over subdomains, that are then recomposed into the whole domain, by smoothing the discontinuities at the boundaries between partitions to preserve the correlation structure.

Table 4 lists the results of the scalability test performed on randomField, with the *standard* and *localized* approaches respectively (i.e. by generating a unique random field over the entire domain (*standard* approach) or by generating independent realizations over subdomains (*localized* approach)). This scalability test was performed by running the generation code on OCCIGEN cluster.

The information above mentioned testifies the efficiency and scalability of the computational platform we aim at exploiting, conformingly with Ceci the performances required to submit this project as Demande d’Attribution de Ressources Informatiques.

9. <http://fftw.org/>

Cores	Nodes	Generation Time (s)	
		Standard	Localized
16	1×10^6	0.86	6.57
32	2×10^6	1.55	13.87
256	2×10^7	356.43	159.98
2048	1×10^8	–	2037.48
4096	3×10^8	–	3299.04

Table 4: Weak scalability analysis for the random field generation (Machine : OCCIGEN Intel E5-2690 (2.6 GHz) / $\sim 50 \times 10^3$ cores). Standard : wall-time required to generate a single random field over the entire domain. Localized : wall-time time required to generate the random field with the localized approach mentioned in the text.

5 Specifics for the demanded allocation

The reference test case to estimate the allocation is O5 simulation (see Table 2). For this simulation, ≈ 81100 hours CPU-time were necessary (≈ 20 hours wall-time, on 4000 MPI-cores), for 20.0 seconds of real earthquake. To have an idea of the machine allocation required, some information related to the O5 simulations are reported in Table 5 and Table 6. Table 6 lists the computational resources employed to perform the simulation described.

N_E	N_D	$\mathcal{L}_x \cdot \mathcal{L}_y \cdot \mathcal{L}_z$ [km^3]	$\Delta_x^{min} \cdot \Delta_y^{min} \cdot \Delta_z^{min}$ [m^3]
$\approx 4.5 \cdot 10^6$	$\approx 9.8 - 13.5 \cdot 10^9$	$44 \times 44 \times 63$	$130 \times 130 \times 35$

Table 5: Mesh characteristics for the earthquake scenario of Kefalonia island [39] (model O5). N_E : number of hexaedrael elements (8-nodes); N_D : number of Degrees of Freedom ($10 \times 10 \times 10$ GLL $\times 3$ per element); \mathcal{L}_x - \mathcal{L}_y - \mathcal{L}_z domain sizes; Δ_x^{min} - Δ_y^{min} - Δ_z^{min} minimum element sizes.

Please note that the scalar computational time t_{CPU} indicated in Table 6 represents the total elapsed CPU time as equivalent mono-processor, i.e. it is the sum of the running times of each processor (in the presented case, 4000 MPI processors), according to the equation :

$$t_{CPU} = t_{wall} \times N_{MPI} \quad (3)$$

where t_{wall} is the wall-time (also called *elapsed* time) and N_{MPI} is number of MPI processes.

N_{MPI}	M_{MPI} [Gb]	t_{CPU} [h]	HD [Gb]	N_{FILES}
4000	1	≈ 81100	≈ 3500	≈ 15000

Table 6: Computational resources allocated for one simulation of the Argostoli earthquake scenario. N_{MPI} : number of MPI processes; M_{MPI} : memory per MPI process; t_{CPU} mono-processor equivalent CPU-time (for 20.0 seconds of real earthquake) computed as $walltime \times N_{MPI}$ (see Eq. 3); HD : Hard-Disk allocation; N_{FILES} : number of files generated.

The HD in Table 6 refers to the total storage required for : (1) saving results (typically, 2000 Gb for velocity contour maps close to the surface topography, 5 Gb for the time histories), (2) storing mesh files and heterogeneous mechanical properties (≈ 10 -20 Gb) and to perform save&restart procedure (state variables must be saved all over the domain, which leads to around ≈ 2000 Gb). All files saved are in HDF5 format. The amount of file generated N_{FILES} includes the protections, that are immediately erased after the run, and the mesh files, which are the same for each simulation.

In this project, we will run 22 simulations (as explained in Section 3), corresponding to 2 earthquake scenarios with extended faults and 10 point-source simulations for EGF method. Considering O5 as reference simulation, but given the need for longer simulations ($t_{EQK} = 30$ s of real earthquake instead of $t_{EQK} = 20$ s), we estimate an amount of 121650 CPU hours per run. Therefore, we demand 3000000 scalar hours (CPU-time) and we aim at performing simulations over 4800 cores (average) and 10000 cores (peak) Intel Cascade Lake 6248 - 2.5 GHz. Table 7 summarizes the estimated allocation, based on a computational grid with an estimated number of DOFs of $\approx 2 \cdot 10^{10}$ and for simulations of 30 seconds of real earthquake. Therefore the $t_{CPU}^{10} = 121650$ h computed for

Case Study	N_S	t_{CPU} [h]	N_{MPI}	N_{FILES}
Cadarache	30	121650	4000	15000

Table 7: Set of foreseen simulations for the project proposal. The Argostoli basin is taken as reference. N_S : number of simulations per test case (30 in total); t_{CPU} : mono-processor equivalent CPU-time per each run, computed as $walltime \times N_{MPI}$ (see Eq. 3); N_{MPI} : number of cores MPI employed per run; N_{FILES} : number of file generated per run.

4000 MPI cores in Table 6 allow us to run around 25 simulations, so as to save enough margin to run a few extra simulations for the EGF method (since 10 point-sources are an arbitrary estimation). In terms of memory, we need to save approximately 1500 Gb of the actual 3500 Gb demanded per run (we erase the protections). Therefore we estimated 30 Tb maximum of hard-disk allocation. No permanent storage is required (data will be progressively repatriated).

Concerning visualization, we would like to have access to a GPU visualization node, with GPU accelerated `paraview` software. Contour plots have been effectively rendered by GPU accelerated `paraview` software up until 4 Tb on OCCIGEN visualization node(Broadwell E5-2690 V4@2.6GHz, 1 GPUs Nvidia Tesla P100 PCIe 12Go).

10. mono-processor equivalent CPU-time per each run, computed as *walltime* \times number of processors, see Eq. 3

Bibliographie

Références

- [1] Murray ROSENBLATT. “Remarks on a multivariate transformation”. In : *The annals of mathematical statistics* 23.3 (1952), p. 470-472.
- [2] K. AKI et B. CHOUET. “Origin of coda waves: Source, attenuation, and scattering effects”. In : *Journal of Geophysical Research* 80.23 (1975), p. 3322-3342. DOI : [10.1029/JB080i023p03322](https://doi.org/10.1029/JB080i023p03322).
- [3] K. AKI et P.G. RICHARDS. *Quantitative Seismology-Theory and Methods*. T. I-II. Books in Geology. San Francisco (USA) : W.H Freeman et Company, 1980.
- [4] Masanobu SHINOZUKA et George DEODATIS. “Simulation of stochastic processes by spectral representation”. In : *Applied Mechanics Reviews* 44.4 (1991), p. 191-204.
- [5] K. YOMOGIDA et J. T. ETGEN. “3-D wave propagation in the Los Angeles basin for the Whittier-Narrows earthquake”. In : *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America* 83.5 (1993), p. 1325-1344.
- [6] M. SHINOZUKA et G. DEODATIS. “Simulation of multi-dimensional Gaussian stochastic fields by spectral representation”. In : *Applied Mechanics Reviews* 49 (1996), p. 29-53.
- [7] Michel SÉBRIER, Abdessamad GHAFIRI et Jean-Louis BLES. “Paleoseismicity in France: fault trench studies in a region of moderate seismicity”. In : *Journal of Geodynamics* 24.1-4 (1997), p. 207-217.
- [8] Jacobo BIELAK et al. “Domain Reduction Method for Three-Dimensional Earthquake Modeling in Localized Regions. Part 1: Theory”. In : *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America* 93.2 (2003), p. 817-840.
- [9] Dimitri KOMATITSCH, Seiji TSUBOI, Chen Ji et Jeroen TROMP. “A 14.6 Billion Degrees of Freedom, 5 Teraflops, 2.5 Terabyte Earthquake Simulation on the Earth Simulator”. In : *Proceedings of the 2003 ACM/IEEE Conference on Supercomputing*. SC '03. Phoenix, AZ, USA : ACM, 2003, p. 4-. DOI : [10.1145/1048935.1050155](https://doi.org/10.1145/1048935.1050155). URL : <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1048935.1050155>.
- [10] Seiji TSUBOI, Dimitri KOMATITSCH, Chen Ji et Jeroen TROMP. “Broadband modeling of the 2002 Denali fault earthquake on the Earth Simulator”. In : 139.3-4 (2003), p. 305-313. DOI : [10.1016/j.pepi.2003.09.012](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pepi.2003.09.012).
- [11] Hari SUNDAR, Rahul S SAMPATH et George BIROS. “Bottom-up construction and 2: 1 balance refinement of linear octrees in parallel”. In : *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing* 30.5 (2008), p. 2675-2708.
- [12] Carsten BURSTEDDE, Lucas C. WILCOX et Omar GHATTAS. “p4est: Scalable Algorithms for Parallel Adaptive Mesh Refinement on Forests of Octrees”. In : *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing* 33.3 (2011), p. 1103-1133. DOI : [10.1137/100791634](https://doi.org/10.1137/100791634). URL : <https://doi.org/10.1137/100791634>.
- [13] Stéphane MOLLIEUX, Olivier BELLIER, Monique TERRIER, Juliette LAMARCHE, Guillaume MARTELET et Nicolas ESPURT. “Tectonic and sedimentary inheritance on the structural framework of Provence (SE France): Importance of the Salon-Cavaillon fault”. In : *Tectonophysics* 501.1 (2011), p. 1 -16. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tecto.2010.09.008>. URL : <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0040195110003586>.
- [14] K. TSUDA et al. “Modeling 3D Velocity Structure in the Fault Region of the 2007 Niigataken Chuetsu-Oki Earthquake with Folding Structure”. In : *4th IASPEI/IAEE International Symposium-Effects of Surface Geology on Seismic Motion*. 2011, p. 1-11.
- [15] Lawrence HUTCHINGS et Gisela VIEGAS. “Application of empirical Green’s functions in earthquake source, wave propagation and strong ground motion studies”. In : *Earthquake Research and Analysis, New Frontiers in Seismology* (2012), p. 87-140.
- [16] T ICHIMURA, M HORI, PE QUINAY, MLL WIJERATHNE, T SUZUKI et S NOGUCHI. “Comprehensive numerical analysis of fault-structure systems—Computation of the large-scale seismic structural response to a given earthquake scenario—”. In : *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics* 41.4 (2012), p. 795-811. DOI : [10.1002/eqe.1158](https://doi.org/10.1002/eqe.1158).
- [17] P. E. B. QUINAY, T. ICHIMURA, M. HORI, A. NISHIDA et S. YOSHIMURA. “Seismic Structural Response Estimates of a Fault-Structure System Model with Fine Resolution Using Multiscale Analysis with Parallel Simulation of Seismic-Wave Propagation”. In : *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America* 103.3 (2013). doi: 10.1785/0120120216, p. 2094-2110. DOI : [10.1785/0120120216](https://doi.org/10.1785/0120120216).
- [18] R. TABORDA et J. BIELAK. “Ground-Motion Simulation and Validation of the 2008 Chino Hills, California, Earthquake”. In : *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America* 103.1 (2013), p. 131-156. DOI : [10.1785/0120110325](https://doi.org/10.1785/0120110325). URL : <http://www.bssaonline.org/content/103/1/131.abstract>.
- [19] M. VILLANI, E. FACCIOLO, M. ORDAZ et M. STUPAZZINI. “High-Resolution Seismic Hazard Analysis in a Complex Geological Configuration: The Case of the Sulmona Basin in Central Italy”. In : *Earthquake Spectra* 3.4 (2014), p. 1801-1824. DOI : [DOI:10.1193/1112911EQS288M](https://doi.org/10.1193/1112911EQS288M).

- [20] Cédric GUYONNET-BENAIZE, Juliette LAMARCHE, Fabrice HOLLENDER, Sophie VISEUR, Philippe MÜNCH et Jean BORGOMANO. “Three-dimensional structural modeling of an active fault zone based on complex outcrop and subsurface data: The Middle Durance Fault Zone inherited from polyphase Meso-Cenozoic tectonics (southeastern France)”. In : *Tectonics* 34.2 (2015), p. 265-289.
- [21] L PALUDO, V BOUVIER, R COTTEREAU et D CLOUTEAU. “Efficient Parallel Generation of Random Field of Mechanical Properties for Geophysical Application”. In : *6th International Conference on Earthquake Geotechnical Engineering*. 2015.
- [22] R. PAOLUCCI, I. MAZZIERI et C. SMERZINI. “Anatomy of strong ground motion: near-source records and 3D physics-based numerical simulations of the Mw 6.0 May 29 2012 Po Plain earthquake, Italy”. In : *Geophysical Journal International* 203 (2015). doi: 10.1093/gji/ggv405, p. 2001-2020. DOI : [10.1093/gji/ggv405](https://doi.org/10.1093/gji/ggv405).
- [23] Olivier BELLIER et al. “Aléa et risque sismique en Provence: tectonique active et sismotectonique des Failles de la Moyenne Durance et de la Trévaresse”. In : (2016).
- [24] Seiji Tsuboi, Kazuto ANDO, Takayuki MIYOSHI, Daniel PETER, Dimitri KOMATITSCH et Jeroen TROMP. “A 1.8 trillion degrees-of-freedom, 1.24 petaflops global seismic wave simulation on the K computer”. In : *The International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications* 30.4 (2016). doi: 10.1177/1094342016632596, p. 411-422. DOI : [10.1177/1094342016632596](https://doi.org/10.1177/1094342016632596). URL : <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094342016632596>.
- [25] CEA, CENTRALESUPÉLEC, IGP et CNRS. “SEM3D Ver 2017.04 Registered at French Agency for Protection of Programs (Dépôt APP)”. Brev. IDN.FR.001.400009.000.S.P.2018.000.31235. 2017.
- [26] Haohuan FU et al. “18.9Pfpss Nonlinear Earthquake Simulation on Sunway TaihuLight: Enabling Depiction of 18-Hz and 8-meter Scenarios”. In : *Proceedings of the International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis*. SC '17. Denver, Colorado : ACM, 2017, 2:1-2:12. DOI : [10.1145/3126908.3126910](https://doi.org/10.1145/3126908.3126910). URL : <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/3126908.3126910>.
- [27] F. GATTI, F. LOPEZ-CABALLERO, R. PAOLUCCI et D. CLOUTEAU. “Near-source effects and non-linear site response at Kashiwazaki-Kariwa Nuclear Power Plant, in the 2007 Chuetsu-Oki earthquake: evidence from surface and downhole records and 1D numerical simulations”. In : *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering* 16.3 (2017), p. 1105-1135. DOI : [10.1007/s10518-017-0255-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-017-0255-y). URL : <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-017-0255-y>.
- [28] F. GATTI, L. De Carvalho PALUDO, A. SVAY, F. LOPEZ-CABALLERO, R. COTTEREAU et D. CLOUTEAU. “Investigation of the earthquake ground motion coherence in heterogeneous non-linear soil deposits”. In : *Procedia Engineering* 199.Supplement C (2017). X International Conference on Structural Dynamics, EURO-DYN 2017, p. 2354 -2359. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2017.09.232>. URL : <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877705817336822>.
- [29] Tsuyoshi ICHIMURA, Kohei FUJITA, Atsushi YOSHIYUKI, Pher Errol QUINAY, Muneo HORI et Takashi SAKANOE. “Performance Enhancement of Three-Dimensional Soil Structure Model via Optimization for Estimating Seismic Behavior of Buried Pipelines”. In : *Journal of Earthquake and Tsunami* 11.05 (2017). doi: 10.1142/S1793431117500191, p. 1750019. DOI : [10.1142/S1793431117500191](https://doi.org/10.1142/S1793431117500191).
- [30] S. KHAZAIE, R COTTEREAU et D CLOUTEAU. “Numerical observation of the equipartition regime in a 3D random elastic medium, and discussion of the limiting parameters”. In : *Computers & Geosciences* 102 (2017), p. 56 -67. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2017.02.007>. URL : <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0098300417301747>.
- [31] Chiara SMERZINI, Kyriazis PITILAKIS et Kiana HASHEMI. “Evaluation of earthquake ground motion and site effects in the Thessaloniki urban area by 3D finite-fault numerical simulations”. In : *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering* 15.3 (2017). doi: 10.1007/s10518-016-9977-5, p. 787-812. DOI : [10.1007/s10518-016-9977-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-016-9977-5). URL : <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-016-9977-5>.
- [32] Angkeara SVAY et al. “Spatial coherency analysis of seismic ground motions from a rock site dense array implemented during the Kefalonia 2014 aftershock sequence”. In : *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics* 46.12 (2017). ege.2881, p. 1895-1917. DOI : [10.1002/eqe.2881](https://doi.org/10.1002/eqe.2881). URL : <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/eqe.2881>.
- [33] Carsten UPHOFF et al. “Extreme Scale Multi-physics Simulations of the Tsunamigenic 2004 Sumatra Megathrust Earthquake”. In : *Proceedings of the International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis*. SC '17. Denver, Colorado : ACM, 2017, 21:1-21:16. DOI : [10.1145/3126908.3126948](https://doi.org/10.1145/3126908.3126948). URL : <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/3126908.3126948>.
- [34] Alain DUJARDIN, Mathieu CAUSSE, Catherine BERGE-THIERRY et Fabrice HOLLENDER. “Radiation Patterns Control the Near-Source Ground-Motion Saturation Effect”. In : *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America* 108.6 (2018). doi: 10.1785/0120180076, p. 3398. DOI : [10.1785/0120180076](https://doi.org/10.1785/0120180076). URL : <https://dx.doi.org/10.1785/0120180076>.

- [35] F. GATTI, F. LOPEZ-CABALLERO, D. CLOUTEAU et R. PAOLUCCI. “On the effect of the 3-D regional geology on the seismic design of critical structures: the case of the Kashiwazaki-Kariwa Nuclear Power Plant”. In : *Geophysical Journal International* 213.2 (2018). doi: 10.1093/gji/ggy027, p. 1073-1092. DOI : [10.1093/gji/ggy027](https://doi.org/10.1093/gji/ggy027). URL : <https://doi.org/10.1093/gji/ggy027>.
- [36] F. GATTI, S. TOUHAMI, F. LOPEZ-CABALLERO et D. PITILAKIS. “3-D source-to-site numerical investigation on the earthquake ground motion coherency in heterogeneous soil deposits”. In : *9th European Conference on Numerical Methods in Geotechnical Engineering, 25-27 June 2018, Porto (Portugal)*. 2018.
- [37] F. GATTI et al. “Broad-band 3-D earthquake simulation at nuclear site by an all-embracing source-to-structure approach”. In : *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering* 115 (2018). doi: 10.1016/j.soildyn.2018.08.028, p. 263-280. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2018.08.028>. URL : <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0267726118303890>.
- [38] R. PAOLUCCI, F. GATTI, M. INFANTINO, A. G. OZCEBE, C. SMERZINI et M. STUPAZZINI. “Broad-band ground motions from 3D physics-based numerical simulations using Artificial Neural Networks”. In : *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America* 108.(3A) (2018), p. 1272-1286. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1785/0120170293>.
- [39] Sara TOUHAMI, F GATTI, Fernando LOPEZ-CABALLERO, Fabrice HOLLENDER et Edward Marc CUSHING. “Argostoli site, from site test to numerical model: a holistic approach”. In : *Best Practices in Physics-based Fault Rupture Models for Seismic Hazard Assessment of Nuclear Installations: issues and challenges towards full Seismic Risk Analysis*. Cadarache, France, mai 2018. URL : <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01851742>.
- [40] S. TOUHAMI, F. LOPEZ-CABALLERO et D. CLOUTEAU. “A holistic approach of numerical analysis of the geology effects on ground motion prediction : Argostoli site test”. In : *Journal of Seismology* Under review (2020).
- [41] Sara TOUHAMI. “Numerical modeling of seismic field and soil interaction : application to the sedimentary basin of Argostoli (Greece)”. Thèse de doct. CentraleSupélec - Université Paris Saclay, 2020.
- [42] Muneo HORI et Tsuyoshi ICHIMURA. *Application of Macro-Micro Analysis Method to Estimate Strong Motion Distribution and Resulting Structure Response*.